

Cation Exchange Chromatographic Separation of Manganese in Mixed Solvent Systems

A. G. GAIKWAD and S. M. KHOPKAR

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Powai, Bombay-400 076

Cation exchange chromatographic behaviour of manganese(II) on Dowex 50W-X8 was studied in mixed solvent systems. Methanol, ethanol, 2-propanol, acetone, dioxane and tetrahydrofuran in conjunction with 2 *M* hydrochloric acid were used as eluants.

Amongst the non-aqueous solvents tested, acetone, methanol and ethanol proved to be efficient while 2-propanol, dioxane and tetrahydrofuran had no practical utility. The separation of manganese from binary mixture containing alkali metals, alkaline earth metals and some other associated elements was carried out by the process gradient elution as well as selective elution using combinations of different organic solvents. Similarly, separation of multicomponent mixtures of six elements commonly associated with manganese was done by sequential separation in the mixed solvent system.

ALTHOUGH cation exchange chromatographic¹ behaviour of manganese was studied on Dowex 50W-X8, such studies in the mixed solvent systems are lacking.

The exchange constant in methanol and ethanol media was determined² on cationite KU-2. The separation of manganese from nickel³ was effected using this information. Similarly, manganese was separated from copper in acetone-hydrochloric acid solutions⁴. The cation exchange studies for manganese, cobalt and magnesium⁵ was carried out in mineral acids containing alcohols. Manganese was separated from nickel⁶ with glycine. However, cation exchange separations of manganese in mixed solvent systems such as methanol, ethanol, 2-propanol, acetone, dioxane and tetrahydrofuran are lacking. This paper presents such studies. Various interesting separations have also been achieved and reported.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents :

The ion-exchange column (1.4 × 20 cm) was similar to the one described earlier⁷. A digital pH meter (ECIL India, type pH-822) with glass and calomel electrodes was used.

A stock solution of manganese was prepared by dissolving 4.5 g of manganese chloride tetrahydrate in 250 ml distilled water containing 1% hydrochloric acid. It was standardized complexometrically⁸, and was found to contain 5.10 mg/ml of manganese. Dowex 50W-X8 (Dow Chemical Co., Midland, Mich., U.S.A.) 20-50 mesh (H⁺ form) was used.

General procedure :

(a) Procedure for cation exchange studies : An aliquot of the stock solution, containing 10-20 mg of manganese, was sorbed on the column at flow rate

TABLE 1—CATION EXCHANGE STUDIES OF MANGANESE WITH MINERAL ACIDS AS ELUANT

Eluant (<i>M</i>)	Peak elution volume V_{max} , ml	Total elution volume V_t , ml	Manganese recovery (%)	Elution constant (E)	Volume distribution coeff. (D_v)	Weight distribution coefficient (D_w)
HCl	1	200	19.8	—	—	—
	2	75	200	0.58	1.74	1.21
	3-4	50	150	1.08	0.93	0.65
HNO ₃	1	200	17.4	—	—	—
	2	100	225	0.39	2.55	1.77
	3	75	175	0.58	1.74	1.21
	4	50	150	1.08	0.93	0.65
H ₂ SO ₄	1	200	83.9	—	—	—
	2	50	150	1.08	0.93	0.65
	3-4	50	100	1.08	0.93	0.65
HClO ₄	1	200	88.4	—	—	—
	2	100	200	0.39	2.55	1.77
	4	75	175	0.58	1.74	1.21

TABLE 2—CATION EXCHANGE STUDIES OF MANGANESE(II) IN MIXED SOLVENT SYSTEMS

Mn(II) 10.2 mg	Weight of resin = 12.55 g	Column = 1.4 × 20 cm	Resin = Dowex 50 W - X8 (H ⁺ form)			
Organic solvents in (%) with 2 M HCl	Peak elution volume V_{max}, ml	Total elution volume V_t, ml	Manganese recovery (%)	Elution constant (E)	Volume distribution coefficient (D_v)	Weight distribution coefficient (D_w)
Methanol						
20	75	250	100.00	0.58	1.74	1.21
40	75	275	100.19	0.58	1.74	1.21
60	100	300	98.80	0.39	2.55	1.77
80	100	300	93.66	0.39	2.55	1.77
Ethanol						
20	75	250	100.05	0.58	1.74	1.21
40	75	275	99.84	0.58	1.74	1.21
60	100	300	97.06	0.39	2.55	1.77
80	100	300	84.66	0.39	2.55	1.77
2-Propanol						
20	75	250	100.00	0.58	1.74	1.21
40	75	275	99.82	0.58	1.74	1.21
60	100	300	85.17	0.39	2.55	1.77
Acetone						
20	75	250	100.00	0.58	1.74	1.21
40	75	275	100.00	0.58	1.74	1.21
60	100	300	99.95	0.39	2.55	1.77
80	50	225	100.01	1.08	0.93	0.65
1,4-Dioxane						
20	75	250	100.00	0.58	1.74	1.21
40	75	275	99.22	0.58	1.74	1.21
60	50	300	98.36	1.08	0.93	0.65
Tetrahydrofuran						
20	75	250	100.28	0.58	1.74	1.21
40	75	275	99.15	0.58	1.74	1.21
60	100	300	98.07	0.39	2.55	1.77
80	50	250	92.57	1.08	0.93	0.65

Fig. 1. Elution behaviour of manganese(II) on Dowex 50W-X8 with various mixed solvent systems. A : 2 M HCl in 20% non-aqueous solvent ; B : 2 M HCl in 40% non-aqueous solvent ; C : 2 M HCl in 60% non-aqueous solvent ; D : 2 M HCl in 80% non-aqueous solvent.

of 1 ml/min. The column was washed with water. Manganese from the column was eluted with various mineral acids (Table 1) and with mixtures of 2 M hydrochloric acid with various concentrations of non-aqueous solvents like methanol, ethanol, acetone, 2-propanol, dioxane or tetrahydrofuran (Table 2 ; Fig. 1). The effluent lot was collected in 25 ml fractions and in each case ten to twelve fractions were collected. The fractions were evaporated almost to dryness prior to the determination of manganese by complexometric titration⁸.

(b) Procedure for separations : An aliquot of solution containing mixture of two or more cations along with manganese was passed on the column at the flow rate of 1 ml/min. The specific eluants as described under various separations, were then passed through the column to elute each element at the flow rate of 2 ml/min. The concentration of a particular element in the eluted solutions was determined quantitatively by an appropriate method, usually involving complexometric titration.

Fig. 2. Sequential separation of zinc, iron(II), copper(II), cobalt(II), manganese and nickel
 0.5 M HNO₃(1) 0.3 M HCl in 90% Acetone(2) 1 M HCl 90% Acetone(3) 1.5 M HCl H₂SO₄(5)
 2 M HCl in 40% Ethanol(4)

Fig. 3. Sequential separation of vanadium(V), uranium(VI), manganese(II), titanium(IV) and scandium(III).

0.5 M HCl in 60% Propanol(Ce) 0.5 M HCl in 80% Acetone(Pb) 2 M HCl in 80% Acetone(Mn) 3 M HCl in 60% Methanol(AI) 3M HCl(Ca)

Fig. 4. Sequential separation of cadmium, lead(II), manganese(II), aluminium and calcium

Results and Discussion

The elution constant (E) and distribution coefficients (D_v , D_w) were evaluated as described earlier¹. From their knowledge, it was possible to have selectivity scale for mineral acids as eluants, as well as for non-aqueous solvents mixed with

2 M hydrochloric acid. The scale was H₂SO₄ > HCl > HNO₃ > HClO₄ for mineral acids and acetone > ethanol > methanol > 1,4-dioxane > tetrahydrofuran > 2-propanol for non-aqueous solvents.

Amongst the eluants tested for manganese the complexing organic acids were found to be poor¹. The mineral acids in the concentration range of 0 to 1 M were poor eluants, but at 2 M acidity elution was quantitative for all acids with the exception of perchloric acid. The optimum concentration of mineral acid was 2 M. The most practical eluant was hydrochloric acid. Hence it was used in all investigations along with non-aqueous solvents. A lower concentration of hydrochloric acid could be used provided it was used in conjunction with non-aqueous solvents.

There are several advantages of carrying out cation exchange chromatographic separations in mixed solvent systems as described earlier⁷. Among the various non-aqueous solvents used, it was noted that acetone was the most promising because the elution of manganese was quantitative with 20 to 80% acetone in 2 M hydrochloric acid. Ethanol and methanol were the next best from the view point of separation. With 2-propanol the flow rate was extremely low at higher concentrations. Though it was possible to get the separation with 1,4-dioxane, the problem of two phase formation was encountered. With tetrahydrofuran system, the extraction was not generally quantitative in higher concentration. Further, it was possible to elute manganese quantitatively with 0.75 to 2 M hydrochloric acid, only in the presence of 80 to 90% acetone. The methanol and ethanol system was effective for separation of multicomponent mixtures.

During ion exchange separation, it was noted that manganese was strongly bound to the resin in comparison to other elements and was therefore eluted later in certain separations. In the few instances where manganese was weakly bound to the resin, it was eluted first before elution of interfering ion and was thus separated in mixture. Few such separations are illustrated in the following part.

Separation of manganese in acetone media: Vanadium(V), mercury(II), indium(III), bismuth(III) and lithium were separated from manganese in acetone media by selective elution of these ions as they were weakly bound. On passing a binary mixture of manganese with any of these ions on the column, they were taken up by the resin. They were first eluted with 0.5 M hydrochloric acid, followed by the elution of manganese with 2 M hydrochloric acid in 80% acetone. Zinc and cadmium were separated from manganese by first eluting zinc and cadmium with 0.5 M hydrochloric acid in 80% methanol, with subsequent elution of manganese with 2 M hydrochloric acid in 80% acetone.

Uranium(VI), iron(III), cobalt(II), copper(II), gallium(III) and lead(II) were separated from manganese by eluting these elements with 0.5 M hydrochloric acid in 80% acetone [0.5 M hydrochloric acid in 90% acetone for uranium(VI) and cobalt(II)], with subsequent elution of manganese with 2 M hydrochloric acid in 80% acetone.

TABLE 3—ION EXCHANGE SEPARATION OF MANGANESE(II) FROM VARIOUS OTHER ELEMENTS IN BINARY MIXTURES

Mn(II) = 5.1 mg

Foreign ion	Amount added mg	Manganese found mg	Recovery of manganese (%)	Eluant for other elements	Eluant for manganese
V(V)	50.00	5.0	98.0	0.5 M HCl	2 M HCl in 80% acetone
Hg(II)	35.00	5.1	100.0	"	"
In(III)	54.00	5.1	100.0	"	"
Bi(III)	65.00	5.1	100.0	"	"
Li	50.50	5.1	100.0	"	"
Fe(III)	62.40	5.1	100.0	0.5 M HCl in 80% acetone	"
Zn(II)	65.20	5.1	100.0	0.5 M HCl in 80% methanol	"
Cd(II)	60.50	5.1	100.0	"	"
U(VI)	45.30	5.1	100.0	0.5 M HCl in 90% acetone	"
Co(II)	12.00	5.0	98.0	"	"
Cu(II)	65.00	5.1	100.0	0.5 M HCl in 80% acetone	"
Ga(III)	45.00	5.1	100.0	"	"
Pb(II)	56.30	5.1	100.0	"	"
Na	45.00	5.0	98.0	4 M HCl	0.75 M HCl in 90% acetone
K	50.00	5.1	100.0	"	"
Rb	40.40	5.1	100.2	"	"
Cs	45.40	5.0	99.1	"	"
Be	30.40	5.1	100.0	"	"
Ca	65.00	5.1	100.0	"	"
Mg	50.40	5.1	100.0	"	"
Al	65.30	5.1	100.0	"	"
Ti(IV)	45.00	5.1	100.0	8 M HCl	"
Ni(II)	45.30	5.0	98.0	4 M HCl	"
Sc(III)	50.00	5.1	100.0	8 M HCl	3 M HCl in 60% ethanol
Y(III)	50.00	5.1	100.0	"	"
Zr(IV)	50.40	5.1	100.0	"	"
Th(IV)	60.80	5.1	100.0	"	"
Ce(III)	60.40	5.1	100.0	"	"
Sr(III)	60.00	5.1	100.0	"	"
Ba(II)	65.40	5.1	100.0	"	"

In contrast, in acetone media some elements were taken up strongly by the resin and were eluted later. Manganese was separated from sodium, potassium, rubidium, caesium, beryllium, calcium, magnesium, aluminium, titanium(IV) and nickel(II) by its elution with 0.75 M hydrochloric acid in 90% acetone, followed by elution of all the listed ions with 4 M hydrochloric acid. In case of titanium it was necessary to use 8 M hydrochloric acid (Table 3).

Separation in ethanol media : Since scandium(III), yttrium(III), zirconium(IV), thorium(IV), cerium(III), strontium(III) and barium(II) were strongly retained on the resin in comparison to manganese, the latter was first eluted with 3 M hydrochloric acid in 60% ethanol, followed by elution of all the elements with 8 M hydrochloric acid (Table 3).

Separation of manganese from multi-component mixtures : Manganese was separated from several multicomponent mixtures in the following manner :

A mixture of zinc, iron(III), copper(II), cobalt(II), manganese(II) and nickel(II) was sorbed

on the column. Zinc was first eluted with 0.5 M hydrochloric acid in 80% ethanol, then iron(III) was eluted with 0.2 M hydrochloric acid in 80% acetone, copper(II) with 0.5 M hydrochloric acid in 80% acetone, cobalt(II) with 0.3 M hydrochloric acid in 90% acetone, manganese with 0.75 M hydrochloric acid in 90% acetone and finally nickel(II) was eluted with 2 M hydrochloric acid.

A mixture of vanadium(V), uranium(VI), manganese(II), titanium(IV) and scandium(III) was sorbed on the column. Vanadium(V) was eluted with 0.5 M nitric acid, uranium(VI) with 0.3 M hydrochloric acid in 90% acetone, manganese with 1 M hydrochloric acid in 90% acetone, titanium(IV) with 2 M hydrochloric acid in 40% ethanol and finally, scandium(III) was eluted with 1.5 M sulphuric acid.

A mixture of cadmium(II), lead(II), manganese(II), aluminium and calcium was passed on the column. Cadmium was eluted with 0.5 M hydrochloric acid in 60% 2-propanol, lead(II) with 0.5 M hydrochloric acid in 80% acetone, manganese with

Fig. 5. Sequential separation of iron(III), manganese(II), magnesium and barium(II).

TABLE 4—SEPARATION OF MANGANESE FROM MULTICOMPONENT MIXTURES

Sl. No.	Element	Amount added mg	Amount found mg	Recovery %	Eluant
1.	Zn(II)	10.00	10.00	100.00	0.5 M HCl in 80% methanol
	Fe(III)	9.20	9.20	100.00	0.2 M HCl in 80% acetone
	Cu(II)	10.06	9.90	99.00	0.5 M HCl in 80% acetone
	Co(II)	8.80	8.70	98.86	0.3 M HCl in 90% acetone
	Mn(II)	10.20	10.10	99.01	0.75 M HCl in 90% acetone
2.	Ni(II)	9.40	9.40	100.00	2 M HCl
	V(V)	10.00	10.00	100.00	0.5 M HNO ₃
	U(VI)	9.80	9.70	98.98	0.3 M HCl in 90% acetone
	Mn(II)	10.20	10.20	100.00	1 M HCl in 90% acetone
	Ti(IV)	9.60	9.50	98.96	2 M HCl in 40% ethanol
3.	Sc(III)	10.00	10.00	100.00	1.5 M H ₂ SO ₄
	Cd(II)	10.00	10.00	100.00	0.5 M HCl in 60% 2-propanol
	Pb(II)	10.30	10.20	99.02	0.5 M HCl in 80% acetone
	Mn(II)	10.20	10.20	100.00	2 M HCl in 80% acetone
	Al(II)	9.40	9.40	100.00	3 M HCl in 60% methanol
4.	Ca(II)	10.50	10.40	99.05	3 M HCl
	Fe(III)	9.20	9.20	100.00	0.5 M HCl in 80% acetone
	Mn(II)	10.20	10.20	100.00	1 M HCl in 90% acetone
	Mg(II)	10.00	9.90	99.00	3 M HCl in 40% ethanol
	Ba(II)	10.40	10.30	99.03	3 M HNO ₃

2 M hydrochloric acid in 80% acetone, aluminium with 3 M hydrochloric acid in 60% methanol and finally calcium with 3 M hydrochloric acid.

A mixture of iron(III), manganese(II), magnesium and barium was passed on the column and elution was carried out for iron(III) with 0.5 M hydrochloric acid in 80% acetone, manganese(II) with 1 M hydrochloric acid in 90% acetone, magnesium with 3 M hydrochloric acid in 40% ethanol and finally, barium with 3 M nitric acid (Table 4 ; Fig. 5).

In all the above separations the total volume of the eluant used was 250 ml. Invariably, the analysis of elements was done by complexometry with the exception of alkali and alkaline earth elements which were determined by flame emission spectroscopy.

The separation of manganese from iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II), vanadium(V), titanium(IV), aluminium and lead(II) was significant as these are associated with it in alloys. The isolation of manganese from iron(III) and barium was important as it occurs with them in minerals.

The overall separations required 3 to 4 hr. The relative standard deviation was $\pm 1.5\%$.

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